

TURNING LIGHT INTO LIFE:

Sustainable Production of Purple Bacteria for Future Food and Feed

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Purple4Life - Innovative, sustainable, and circular production of purple phototrophic bacteria as a health-promoting ingredient for food and feed applications

Purple4Life intends to develop a new health-promoting ingredient from purple bacteria. This project has been selected for funding by the European Union out of 57 submitted to the CBE JU Call 2024. 12 organisations from all over Europe will work together to complete this ambitious project by 2029.

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Pablo de Olavide University
Slovak Medical University
Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação
National Research Council of Italy
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Figure 1: Organisations involved in the Purple4Life project. Created in BioRender.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework of Purple4Life. Created in BioRender.

Background

According to reports from the European Environment Agency, agriculture, the primary sector of food production systems, is responsible for more than 10% of the greenhouse gas emissions. The impact of agriculture on the environment is also due to the use of chemical fertilisers (negatively impacting the nitrogen cycle and eutrophication) and pesticides (accumulating in ground and surface water), of large surfaces of arable land (competing with the protection of natural habitat), or via the emissions of ammonia in the atmosphere. Feeding humanity efficiently and continuously only intensifies these pressures, especially as global demand for food rises and the need for healthier ingredients grows. This complex equation can only be addressed through breakthroughs in food production and the development of innovative, environmentally responsible solutions.

Recognising this gap, the Purple4Life project is committed to contributing to the sustainable transition of the European food production strategy by paving the way for the use of innovative, healthy, and circularly and sustainably produced ingredients for food and feed through the use of Purple Phototrophic Bacteria (PPB).

PPBs are today recognised by experts in the field as high-potential actors in the circular bio-based economy, thanks to their very high metabolic versatility and their capacity to convert various substrates into high-added-value biomass efficiently. Because they utilize light as an energy source, their carbon conversion efficiency can approach 100%, thereby surpassing any other heterotrophic (non-light-based) resource recovery biosystem or conventional agricultural practices. Their cultivation would also not depend on or compete with agricultural land and would not contribute to nitrogen emissions. However, the production of PPB is currently not economically viable due to the associated operational costs and capital expenses. The phototrophic capacity of PPB is thus both an opportunity and a challenge. Purple4Life will demonstrate both the feasibility of introducing PPB in the food and feed production system and the benefits in terms of societal and environmental impact. The Purple4Life project will evaluate the feasibility, safety, benefits, and impact of using PPB as new health-promoting and sustainable ingredients for feed and food applications, focusing on Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) and carotenoids.

The Purple4Life project has the following specific objectives (SO):

SO1: Develop innovative circular and sustainable bioprocesses to produce food-grade CoQ10/ carotenoids-rich purple bacteria by upcycling industrial by-products

SO2: Evaluate the health benefits in humans of consuming CoQ10 and carotenoids from purple bacteria

SO3: Evaluate the beneficial effects of purple bacteria as a functional feed ingredient in salmonid fish

SO4: To define and minimise the environmental and climate footprint of the use of PPB in the food chain

SO5: Determine the needs and requirements of stakeholders and inform them of the benefits of introducing purple bacteria in the food chain

SO3: Evaluate the beneficial effects of purple bacteria as a functional feed ingredient in salmonid fish

Aquaculture is a rapidly growing industry essential for meeting the increasing global demand for seafood, particularly for high-value species such as Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). As wild fish stocks decline and consumer preferences shift toward sustainable sources, there is an urgent need to develop new, efficient, and sustainable feed ingredients that support the growth and health of farmed fish. Current challenges include high mortality rates, especially during the critical adaptation phase when juvenile salmon transition from freshwater to seawater, and the production of high-quality aquafeeds that influence not only fish growth and survival but also their quality and market value. For salmonids, feed must also address pigmentation, as the distinctive pink colour of salmon and trout is an essential quality attribute highly valued by consumers. This pigmentation is primarily achieved through dietary carotenoids. Additionally, farmed fish require robust antioxidant support to combat oxidative stress and maintain overall health. Innovative feed ingredients such as PPB present a promising solution to these challenges.

In Purple4Life, we will evaluate the use of PPB as a functional feed ingredient for Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout, targeting critical issues in aquaculture such as high mortality rates, the need for antioxidants, and the importance of fillet quality and pigmentation. The rationale behind this work package is based on the dual benefits offered by PPB, which contain CoQ10 and carotenoids—two key components that can address these needs. CoQ10 is a powerful antioxidant that enhances fish health and resilience by protecting against oxidative stress, which is especially important during challenging phases like the freshwater-to-seawater transition. Meanwhile, carotenoids contribute to fish pigmentation, a trait crucial for market value in species like salmon and trout.

The research will involve producing and analysing feeds containing PPB, determining safe and suitable dietary inclusion levels, conducting bioavailability trials in juvenile fish, and evaluating the commercial applicability of these feeds in adult fish. Additionally, the project will assess the impact of PPB on fish health, immune response, stress resistance, and fillet quality, focusing mainly on colour. We aim to develop a more sustainable and efficient feeding strategy by incorporating PPB biomass into aquafeeds. This approach seeks not only to improve fish health and product quality but also to support the broader goal of sustainably meeting the growing global demand for seafood. The study will demonstrate how innovative feed ingredients like PPB can play a pivotal role in the sustainable growth of the aquaculture industry.

To achieve these objectives, six different high-quality feeds will be formulated with varying PPB concentrations for four feeding trials. Inclusion levels will range from 0.5 to 10 g/100g for juvenile salmon and trout, and approximately 1–2 g/100g for adult fish. Between 250 and 300 kilograms of PPB-enriched feed will be produced. The growth performance and health status of 1,800 juvenile salmon (around 40 grams each, distributed in 18 tanks) and 360 juvenile trout (about 150 grams each, also in 18 tanks) will be assessed across the different PPB levels. Simultaneously, the bioavailability and deposition of CoQ10 and carotenoids derived from PPB in fish tissues will be measured. Adult salmon and trout—210 and 120 individuals respectively, housed in six tanks each and weighing between 1.2 and 1.5 kilograms—will be monitored for growth and health while fed diets containing approximately 1–2 g/100g PPB.

Purple4Life: Are purple bacteria suitable as functional ingredients for fish?

Figure 3: Experimental design of work package 4: Evaluation of purple phototrophic bacteria as functional ingredients in fish feed; Created in BioRender. Lutfi, E. (2025)

Ultimately, the project aims to establish PPB as a stable, oxidation-resistant feed additive enriched with CoQ10 and carotenoids, defining safe and effective inclusion levels for aquaculture feeds. This aligns with broader goals to create sustainable bio-based value chains, improve resource efficiency, and deliver innovative feed solutions with enhanced functional properties compared to existing alternatives.

By introducing sustainably produced PPB into fish feeds, the project expects to improve fish health and growth rates, creating economic advantages for producers while offering nutritional benefits for consumers.

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